

ADAPTATION READINESS LEVEL SELF-ASSESSMENT TEST

PROBLEM ENCOUNTERED AND OBJECTIVE

Several stakeholders in the food packaging sector often face challenges in adopting sustainable packaging, recycling, and reuse practices due to regulatory complexity, lack of awareness, and limited access to best practices. Assessing their current engagement and identifying improvement areas can be difficult. The self-assessment questionnaire helps organisations evaluate their Adaptation Readiness Level in these key areas, classifying them as Rookie, Player, or Expert. The goal is to provide tailored training materials and resources, enabling businesses to enhance their sustainability strategies, meet industry standards, and contribute to a circular economy.

MAIN RESULTS / OUTCOMES

The self-assessment provides organisations with a clear understanding of their sustainability progress in sustainability packaging strategies, recycling, and reuse. Based on their responses, stakeholders are classified into Rookie, Player, or Expert levels, allowing them to identify strengths and areas for improvement. The key outcome is access to tailored training materials and resources, aligned with each organisation's readiness level. These materials support users in advancing their sustainability strategies fostering a more circular and responsible approach to packaging.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Organisations can maximise the benefits of this self-assessment tool by completing the questionnaire thoroughly to determine their sustainability level in Sustainable Packaging Strategies, Recycling, and Reuse. Based on the results (Rookie, Player, or Expert), they can explore the tailored training materials provided to strengthen their knowledge and improve their sustainability practices. These insights can be used to set clear objectives, enhance packaging strategies, and align with industry standards. Regular reassessments will help track progress and refine approaches over time. By engaging with this tool, organisations can optimise packaging solutions, improve sustainability performance, and contribute to a more circular economy.

Further information

Link to Self-Assessment: <https://stopp-project.eu/adaptation-readiness-level-self-assessment-test/>

About this abstract

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STOPP is a Horizon Europe project aiming to transform food plastic packaging through the "5 Rs": Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. Aligned with the EU's Packaging Directive, it develops training materials and strategies to promote circular economy solutions. Engaging stakeholders, STOPP advances recycling, reusable packaging, and consumer awareness for sustainable food packaging.

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